

Wet spirometer

Figure A Wet Spirometer

Figure B Transparent and cross-sectional view of wet spirometer

A
Transparent view of wet spirometer

B
Cross-sectional view of wet spirometer

INCO

Modified spirometer

Figure C Different views of the modified spirometer (without the airflow control system)

A
Front and cross-sectional views (with bell and without stand)

B
Front view (with stand and without bell)

C
Oblique view

D
Horizontal cross-sectional view

E
Vertical cross-sectional view

Computerised spirometer